

Killing representative democracy? Party switching and MP's replacements in the Polish parliament¹

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Abstract

Studies concerning the dynamics of party systems between parliamentary elections are usually based on legislative party switching analyses. This issue was considered and proved in some Western European case studies as well as in some comparative analyses dedicated to the parliaments in the consolidated democracies. But the personal structures of the parliaments in the East-Central European countries are impacted by more than just party switching processes. In this article we propose adopting a broader concept of intraparlimentary volatility, which includes both party switching and replacements of parliamentary mandates. Using data from a full term, 2011–2015, we reconstructed chronological changes in the personal structure of the lower house of the Polish parliament, placing them on a specially created timeline with the intervals marked for each month and distinguishing between change resulted from party switching and replacement of parliamentary mandate. During the period we analyzed the number of independent deputies and the number of parties in the parliament increase alongside with the approaching of the next election. We claim this indicates a stable level of intraparlimentary volatility – immanent for the party systems between parliamentary elections – but this could rise when some special occurrences (i.e. other types of elections or splits within the relevant political party) take place.

Keywords

representative democracy; party system; political parties; party switching; Poland

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Introduction

Many voters reasonably expect results of parliamentary elections to reflect the distribution of political preferences of citizens. The deformation of the will of the voters is, however, inevitable. On the one hand, it can be caused by various elements of the electoral system (Nohlen, 1989). On the other hand, during the term of the parliament it can result from the behavior of the members of parliament (MPs), who – if there is any legal possibility – change their party affiliation. Such change at the parliamentary level – labeled by political scientists as “party switching” – can not only distort the political will of citizens but can also result in deeper transformations of the party system. It might be the reason for the renegotiation of the coalition cabinet’s agreement, for changes in parliamentary alliances, for the reconstruction of the government, or it can even lead to changing the government or holding early parliamentary elections.

It is worth mentioning that party switching is limited by formal rules regulating the exercise of parliamentary mandate (Janda, 2009). However, it is important to emphasize that such an effect is caused not only by party switching, but also by all changes in personal parliamentary structure occurring between parliamentary elections. Because of this, in our research we broaden the perspective focused on party switching and add to it an important new phenomenon – the loss of the parliamentary mandate and its replacement.

We propose the term “intraparliamentary volatility”, defined as a change in the personal parliamentary structure which is reflected in a difference between the primary personal parliamentary structure determined by the parliamentary election results and the personal parliamentary structure observed in the parliament after a specific period of time. Interparliamentary volatility is caused by two factors – party switching and the loss of parliamentary mandates. It is always caused by individual occurrences, and it is always a direct result of an individual decision and behavior. Therefore, we can focus on this phenomenon from the individual perspective, researching motives and social or demographic variables influencing it. However, the other possible way to explaining and measuring the effects of intraparliamentary volatility is from the perspective of whole political system – we can examine its impact on political party relevance or on the efficiency of the parliament’s chambers. In this article we adopt this second perspective.

Literature review

Since Seymour Martin Lipset and Stein Rokkan have proposed their well-known hypothesis concerning the “freeze” of Western European party systems (Lipset & Rokkan, 1967), possible changes in party systems and factors influencing such changes became a popular research topic (Chiaromonte & Emanuele, 2015; Dalton & Weldon, 2007; Janda, 1980; Smith, 1989). Similar studies, with special regard to the peculiarities of the new democracies’ party systems, were also devoted to the countries of Central and Eastern Europe (O’Dwyer, 2014; Olson, 1998; Turovsky, 2011), including the case of Poland (Antoszewski, 2012; Domański, 2008; Szczerbiak, 2001).

These studies indicated multiple factors and mechanisms determining the functioning of the aforementioned party systems, such as the degree of their stability and institutionalization (Bértoa & Enyedi, 2014; Luna, 2014), the size of the existing parties and the degree of party system fragmentation (Anckar, 2000), as well as the impact of external components – e.g., media agents (Brug et al., 2006) or interest groups (Champagne, 2009).

Many authors studying party systems conducted their research mainly with regard to focal points – the results of parliamentary elections. Furthermore, previous studies concerning the dynamics of party systems between elections were mainly confined to neo-institutional perspectives of political

parties or to analyses of the behavior of entities constituting them. It is because of the fact that widely used methodological tools were elaborated mostly in order to examine relatively stable, Western European party systems.

Nevertheless, as various examples show us, party systems in Central and East European countries (including Poland), which function in the context of unconsolidated democracy, are still in development. There are noticeably more changes within these party systems during a parliamentary term, which in fact makes scientific analyses based only on electoral results more or less incomplete.

Recognizing this limitation of the existing theoretical models, scholars decided to consider new problems and new perspectives. One of them is the analysis of party switching, which is understood as “any recorded change in party affiliation on the part of a politician holding or competing for elective office” (Schofield, 2009, p. 8). The initial research focused on categorizing causes of this phenomenon and was primarily theoretical in nature (Aldrich & Bianco, 1992), but quickly evolved into two more elaborated approaches: strategic and institutional studies (Mershon, 2014: 419).

Adopting the strategic approach, scholars analyzed the motivations of politicians who changed their party affiliation (Heller & Mershon, 2005; Laver & Benoit, 2003), the way they synchronize collective actions, as well as patterns of such behavior (Schofield, 2009). Furthermore, scholars were also interested in the influence of parliamentary cycles on party switching (Mershon & Shvetsova, 2005, 2008) and in the effects of pre-election polls on the frequency of such behavior (McMenamin & Gwiazda, 2011).

Taking the institutional approach, researchers focused on macro-factors influencing party switching, such as the level of party system institutionalization (Hicken, 2014) and its fragmentation (Mejía Acosta, 2009). Authors also analyzed the way party switching is determined by differences in various electoral systems (McLaughlin, 2011; Schofield, 2009) and how this phenomenon influences the legislative process (Ilonszki, 2007).

Additionally, the scholars who adopted both approaches conducted cross-national comparative studies and created analytical models (Mershon & Shvetsova, 2013; O’Brien & Shomer, 2013), which were helpful in verifying hypotheses assuming that politicians move more often from smaller to larger parties (Heller & Mershon, 2005; McElroy, 2003) and MPs of the ruling parties are less likely to change their affiliation (Mejía Acosta, 2004; Thames, 2007).

Theoretical and methodological background

As we have already mentioned, studies concerning dynamics of party systems at the parliamentary level – expressed in changes of party affiliation between elections – prove the party switching approach to be too narrow. It considers only changes in the party affiliation of MPs and it does not include the loss of their parliamentary mandates.

This latter phenomenon may result from: a) taking another office (depending on constitutional arrangements, which may allow combining offices, such as being a Prime Minister and accepting ministerial office, or may make it impossible, as in the case of a MP taking up position in the local government or in the European Parliament), b) a loss of the mandate by a judicial decision, c) a death, d) a resignation from the mandate due to other reasons (e.g., personal or health problems).

Depending on the adopted institutional solutions, re-elections may be organized (primarily in majority or mixed electoral systems) or a mandate can be covered by a candidate who in previous elections received the next highest score on the same party list (especially in party-list proportional representation electoral systems). In this context, our understanding of the term “a replacement of

the parliamentary mandate” goes in line with what Van der Hulst has defined as: resignation, mandate recall, and expulsion (Van der Hulst, 2000, pp. 15–25).

Replacement of a parliamentary mandate does not necessarily result in a change in proportions between different parliamentary groups (for example: if party X has 50 seats and one of its MPs dies, then she/he is replaced by a “new” MP who can be, depending on the electoral system, either from the same party list, or newly elected; if the first situation takes place, party X still possess 50 seats). The replacement, however, always determines a change in the personal parliamentary structure (party X still possesses 50 seats, but the “new” MP, who replaced the recently deceased MP, might have different characteristics, for instance he might not be equally loyal, not have the same competences, or have different aims, which inevitably is going to result in different behavior) and, more importantly, it may distort the representativeness of elections (the mandate may be taken by a person who has not received enough votes for being elected).

For this reason, it is necessary to propose a concept different than party switching and refer to the dynamics of party systems between parliamentary elections. In our study we define it as intraparlimentary volatility, a category that encompasses both party switching and replacements of parliamentary mandates. We assume that intraparlimentary volatility is a change in personal parliamentary structure, which is reflected in a difference between the primary personal parliamentary structure, determined by the results of the parliamentary elections, and the personal parliamentary structure after a specific period of time. It is caused by two factors – party switching and replacements of parliamentary mandates.

The aforementioned difference should be examined in two dimensions – time and space. The first concerns the time of exercising the deputies’ mandate, and the second refers to the deputy’s position in the political parliamentary structure. The ideal situation for every deputy in the time dimension is determined by constitutional provisions (their mandate lasts exactly the same amount of time as defined in the constitution). For the space dimension, the ideal situation is defined by being a member of the same political club or circle during the whole parliamentary term.

Thus, structurally speaking, the difference between party switching and intraparlimentary volatility lies in the fact that the first category includes only a change of the MP’s party affiliation in terms of numbers (for example: if A belonging to party X passes to party Y, this is one party switching act, with party X losing one MP and party Y gaining one MP), without taking into account other changes in the personal parliamentary structure (for example: if A belonging to party X is replaced by B belonging to party X, theoretically there was no party switching, but there was a change in the personal parliamentary structure).

To talk about changes that constitute intraparlimentary volatility, we must refer to the subject of changes. In our approach it is a personal parliamentary structure, which is defined as a structure which lasts a specific amount of time and results from an assignment of the individual seats to specific persons affiliated to specific parliamentary groups. The explained intraparlimentary volatility is always initiated by the decisions concerning a single deputy. But the individual behavior (resulting from the change of party affiliation or the mandate loss of a single deputy) always entails a change in the personal structure of the parliamentary group, whose member was this deputy. This level of change we call “party fluctuation”. Evidently, this change also affects the personal structure of the whole parliament. And that is what we call generally as intraparlimentary volatility.

Summarizing, intraparlimentary volatility may be considered as a process with the following levels: (1) at the individual level – a change concerning a single deputy, which results from party switching or replacement of parliamentary mandate; (2) at the party level – a change in the personal

structure of a given parliamentary group, which results from the change of party affiliation of a single deputy or the loss of his/her mandate, which results in his/her replacement by a “new” MP; (3) at the parliamentary level – a change in the personal parliamentary structure caused by the change of an MP’s party affiliation or the loss of her/his mandate, which consequently resulted in her/his replacement by a “new” MP.

Case overview – the Polish party system between 2011 and 2015

The main elements of the Polish system of government are the parliament, the council of ministers (government) and the president (elected by a popular and direct vote). The parliament consists of two chambers – the Sejm (the lower house) and the Senate (the upper house). The Sejm plays a more important role in the Polish political system, not only due to its functions in the legislative process, but also because it grants a vote of confidence or vote of no confidence in the government, which makes the Polish bicameral system asymmetric (Antoszewski, 2012, p. 59).

The Sejm is composed of 460 deputies and the Senate is composed of 100 senators. Elections to the Polish parliament are universal and direct. They are also conducted by secret ballot. Both deputies and senators are elected for a four-year term. Nevertheless, deputies are elected in the proportional representation system using the D’Hondt formula, while senators are elected in a plurality system. It means that if a deputy loses the mandate, she/he is replaced by a new MP who has received the next highest score on the same party list. But if a senator loses the mandate, re-elections are organized in the district where she/he was elected. Mandates of both deputies and senators expire in the case of an MP’s death, loss of passive voting rights, deprivation of the mandate resulting from a final decision of the Tribunal of State, resignation, when an MP is elected to the European Parliament or into local self-government, as well as when she/he holds or is appointed in office, which cannot be held jointly with the mandate of the MP (for example: the President of the National Bank of Poland, the President of the Supreme Audit Office, etc.; see more: art. 103, Constitution of the Republic of Poland). Furthermore, the mandate of MP cannot be held jointly with employment in government administration. This prohibition does not apply to members of the Council of Ministers and secretaries of state. It is also worth mentioning that judges, public prosecutors, officers of the civil service, soldiers, or functionaries of the police or of the services of State protection cannot exercise the mandate of MP.

Describing the political structure of the Polish parliament, we have to emphasize that both deputies and senators may be grouped into clubs (bigger political groups) or circles (smaller political groups). The club in the Sejm may be formed by at least 15 deputies and in the Senate by at least 7 senators. When it comes to circles, they may be formed in the Sejm and in the Senate by at least 3 deputies or 3 senators accordingly. It should be underlined that there are not any legal restrictions concerning moving from one club to another, from one circle to another, from a circle to a club or from a club to a circle. This is why deputies and senators may change their affiliations freely, without any consequences. Such a situation results from the free mandate, which was granted to Polish MPs in art. 104 of the Constitution.

Because of these regulations, the actual political structure of the Polish parliament during a term may be different from that which was determined by the results of elections. Such a situation occurred in 2011, when the election to the Sejm of a 7th term (years 2011–2015) took place. According to the results of elections, which are presented in Table 1, five parties won political representation in this chamber: Civic Platform (*Platforma Obywatelska* – PO), Law and Justice (*Prawo i Sprawiedliwość* – PiS), Palikot Movement (*Ruch Palikota* – RP), Polish Peasant Party (*Polskie Stronnictwo Ludowe* – PSL) and the Democratic Left Alliance (*Sojusz Lewicy Demokratycznej* – SLD).

Between the announcement of the parliamentary election results and the first inaugural sitting of parliament, there were intense intra- and cross-party moves noted. Firstly, the Law and Justice (PiS) leadership removed three MPs (Z. Ziobro, J. Kurski, T. Cymański) from the party for disloyalty, and sixteen newly elected MPs supporting them decided to also leave PiS. They formed the Solidary Poland (Solidarna Polska – SP) parliamentary club in the Sejm. Secondly, two candidates who had gained seats from the Law and Justice lists were not sworn in because they did not want to relinquish their title as retired prosecutors. Their seats were filled only between the first and second sittings of the Sejm. Thirdly, one politician from the Democratic Left Alliance (SLD) decided to leave the party and join the Palikot Movement (RP). Fourthly, in accordance with parliamentary custom, the elected representative of the German minority did not join any club and was affiliated to a group of independent MPs. Sixthly, one of the MPs elected from the Law and Justice list (L. Dorn) decided to join the same independent group. To sum up: before the Polish Sejm of the seventh term had even begun to sit, a total of 21 parliamentary seats (i.e. 4.56% of all seats) had been fluctuated. This is why the initial political structure of the Sejm during its inauguration on November 8th was different than that produced by the results of elections.

Table 1. The political structure of the Sejm after the 2011 elections

Party	Percentage of votes won	Number of seats won	Percentage of seats won	Number of seats at inauguration	Percentage of seats at inauguration
PO	39.18	207	45.00	207	45.00
PiS	29.89	157	34.13	138	30.00
RP	10.02	40	8.69	41	8.91
PSL	8.36	28	6.09	28	6.09
SLD	8.24	27	5.87	26	5.65
SP	---	---	---	16	3.48
Independent	---	---	---	2	0.43
German minority	---	1	0.22	---	---
Other	4.12	---	---	---	---
Total	100.00	460	100.00	458	99.56

Source: Own elaboration.

In the years 2011–2015, as a consequence of various divisions and mergers, several different clubs and circles were also formed in the Sejm. In July 2013 four RP deputies formed a new circle – Dialog Initiative (*Inicjatywa Dialogu* – ID), which existed until December 2013, when all its members entered the PSL club. All deputies who decided to leave the RP club argued that they did not accept the “language of aggression” used by leaders of their former group. In October 2013, leaders of RP changed the name of their party into “Your Turn” (*Twój Ruch* – TR), because they wanted to widen their electorate and abandon the image of the party dominated by one man and his political vision. In July 2014 twelve deputies from SP and three independents, who factually were members of the Poland Together (*Polska Razem* – PR) party, formed a club called “Fair Poland” (*Sprawiedliwa Polska* – SprPol). In March 2015 it was transformed into a club named United Right (*Zjednoczona Prawica* – ZP). The new name was to express the desire of the leaders to build a new party uniting all the right-wing circles

in Poland. In October 2014, eleven deputies, who in the previous month had left TR, formed a new circle in the Sejm, which was called Security and Economy (*Bezpieczeństwo i Gospodarka* – BiG). They argued that they did not accept a new political program proposed by leaders of TR. In June 2015 four deputies, who previously belonged to SLD and TR, formed a new circle called White-Reds (*Biało-Czerwoni* – BC). They decided to create a new political group, because they argued that in the Polish parliament there was no real left-wing organization which could be an alternative for the dominating right-wing parties – PO and PiS.

The formation of new clubs and circles in the Sejm, which resulted in the party switching of MPs, determined a series of changes in the features of the Polish party system. However, this was not the only factor which caused these changes. Also important were the party switching of MPs, who changed their clubs and circles without creating any new political groups, and the losses of deputies' mandates. The analysis of the dynamics of the Sejm's personal structure during the 2011–2015 period allows us to argue that the latter was mainly caused by the appointment or election to new offices. The most important elections which took place during the 7th term of the parliament were the European Parliament (2014), the local and regional (2014), and the presidential (2015) elections.

Research procedure and hypothesis

On the basis of data shared by the Chancellery of the Sejm, we reconstructed chronological changes in the personal structure of the lower house of the Polish parliament, placing them on a specially created timeline with the intervals marked for each month (data are available from the authors upon request). We paid attention to code the change either as the result of party switching, or as the result of replacement of parliamentary mandate. On the same timeline, we also marked elections which took place during the term of the Sejm (European, local/regional, and presidential elections).

In our research we have treated the group of independent deputies as a separate club. Moreover, we did not differentiate clubs from circles – at the moment of their formation we have treated them as an identical parliamentary representation of the political party. It should be noted that the number of deputies in a particular month might not sum up to 460, because a parliamentary mandate remains vacant from the final decision of the Marshal of the Sejm on the loss of parliamentary mandate to the oath of the “new” deputy. In some critical periods, when a lot of deputies lost their mandates (i.e., due to their election to local government), there might be over a dozen or even several dozen vacant parliamentary mandates.

During the analysis of the data and dynamics of parliamentary fluctuation we address the following questions: (1) How large was the group of deputies who changed their party affiliation or replaced their parliamentary mandate? (2) How does parliamentary fluctuation influence the dynamics of the Polish party system between the elections in 2011 and 2015 (with a special focus on differences in parties' size at the beginning and at the end of the term, the number of deputies who have held seats in the parliament, the number of parties that were present in the parliament during its term)? (3) Were there any specific moments during the 7th term of the Polish parliament when intraparlimentary volatility remarkably increased or decreased? (4) Which political party in the parliamentary term 2011–2015 was the most and the least unstable? (5) How does the time that remains to the next parliamentary elections affect the number of independent MPs and the number of parties existing in the parliament?

We test the following hypotheses: (H1) the more institutionalized the party, the more stable the party is; (H2): the number of independent deputies and the number of parties attended in the parliament decreases alongside with the next approaching parliamentary election; (H3) there is a

stable level of intraparlimentary volatility index but it rise after the European, presidential and local elections.

Results and discussion

We start the discussion by underlining that there is a big difference between the terms of party switching and intraparlimentary volatility. In Figure 1 we can observe a count of the number of deputies who changed their party affiliation in any given month. In Figure 2 we show the number of deputies who lost their mandate and were replaced by other candidates from the 2011 election. There are many reasons why deputies changed their party affiliation and why they lost their parliamentary mandate, but we do not want to focus on this problem now.

Figure 1. Party switching of deputies in the Polish Sejm in the term 2011–2015

Source: Own elaboration.

The most important finding is that the number of deputies who changed their party affiliations is highest in July and October 2014, and the number of deputies who lost their mandate is highest in May and December 2014. Thus, it can be clearly seen that it was the European elections (in May 2014) and local elections (in November 2014) during the parliamentary term that were the most important catalyst for intraparlimentary volatility. Thereby, replacement was a direct effect of electoral outcomes (in both the EP and local elections). On the other hand, increased party switching can be seen either as an effect of elections (in the case of EP elections) or as preparation for elections (in the case of local elections).

On the party level, we can observe an interesting phenomenon of increasing party fluctuation together with the number of seats gained after the 2011 elections (see Table 2). The two highest results are achieved by PO and PiS, while the lowest result is recorded for ID. But the result of RP, which is higher than that of SLD and PSL (regardless of higher number of seats at the beginning of the term of parliament) led us to another possible explanation. It can be presumed that the progress in the process of institutionalization of a political party should be treated as a factor influencing parliamentary

fluctuation at the party level. PO, PiS, SLD, and PSL were the most institutionalized Polish political parties in 2011 and it was reflected in the highest values of fluctuation at the party level. Unfortunately, without comparative studies we are not able to prove the hypothesis that there is a simple correlation between the institutionalization of political party in the parliament and the value of fluctuation at the party level.

Figure 2. Mandates replacements in the Polish Sejm during the term 2011–2015

Source: Own elaboration.

Table 2. Parliamentary fluctuation at the party level for all Polish parliamentary parties (2011-2015)

Party	Deputies at the moment of establishing the party in the Sejm	Changes in personal parliamentary structure of the party	Duration of party representation in the Sejm (months)	Average party fluctuation per month
PO	207	66	48	1.3750
PiS	138	69	48	1.4375
RP	41	39	48	0.8125
SLD	26	16	48	0.3333
PSL	28	18	48	0.3750
SP	16	21	33	0.6363
ZP	15	2	15	0.1333
ID	4	0	5	0.0000
BiG	11	6	4	1.5000

Source: Own elaboration.

At the starting point of our research, we supposed that the closer the date of the next parliamentary election, the more stable the party system will be. We presumed that being faced with an upcoming election, deputies will want to strengthen their own opportunities to be re-elected and

consequently they will look for strong and stable political parties, which might be a prospective electoral platform. Nevertheless, the collected data does not confirm our hypothesis. First of all, in Figure 3 we can observe that the number of political parties in the parliament did not decrease alongside the upcoming date of the forthcoming parliamentary elections. On the contrary, half a year before elections a new political group (BC) was established, while PO – the governing and the largest political party – lost a few of their deputies. Secondly,

Figure 4 proves that the specific political group of the independent deputies was increasingly influential and numerous. This is more evidence that there is no direct linkage between the time of election and the stabilization of party system at the parliamentary level.

Figure 3. The number of seats belonging to the political parties in the term 2011–2015

Source: Own elaboration.

In 41 of the 48 months representing the full term, there is no strong deviation from the mean value of the intraparlimentary volatility index at the global parliamentary level. However, there are 7 months when the level of deviation was higher than the mean value of intraparlimentary volatility index (see Figure 5). It means that in those months more deputies from all political parties changed their party affiliation or lost their mandate than in other months. The time of the higher intraparlimentary volatility coincided with particular occurrences. In May 2014 there were elections to the European Parliament and in November 2014 local and regional elections took place, which resulted in changes in the personal parliamentary structure in June 2014, December 2014, and January 2015 (some Polish deputies were elected to the European Parliament or to the local government offices and they had lost their parliamentary mandate). In September 2014 there was a split in the TR which resulted in the formation of a new party, BiG.

Figure 4. The number of independent deputies in the term 2011–2015

Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 5. Deviation of the intraparlimentary volatility index for every month from the mean value of the intraparlimentary volatility index with comparison to the standard deviation

Source: Own elaboration.

Conclusions

In our research we have shown that there is still a great need to broaden the perspective of party system analysis in the period between parliamentary elections. Our proposal is to give a base for the analyses of the intraparlimentary volatility phenomena. We have applied our theoretical and methodological assumptions into the analysis of some specific questions referring to the Polish Sejm in the term 2011–2015. We are sure that our pathway from party switching toward intraparlimentary volatility analyses is needed and prospective.

Using the data from a full term of the Sejm, we showed that in the analyzed period more deputies were stable rather than labile. Moreover, the number of independent deputies and the number of parties existing in the parliament increased alongside with the approaching of the next election (this was surprising for us, and the explanation of this phenomenon will be a challenge for future research). Finally, there seems to be a stable level of intraparlimentary volatility – immanent for the party systems between parliamentary elections – but this could rise in particular contexts (such as the ones defined by other types of elections or by splits within political parties). Unfortunately, without comparative studies we are not able to prove or question the hypothesis that the size of party is correlated to its fluctuation (for instance: the bigger the party, the more stable it is or the smaller the party, the more unstable it is).

Future research should focus on comparative studies concerning intraparlimentary volatility. Political scientists may analyze values of intraparlimentary volatility with regard to different terms of the same parliament (possible question: is there any coincidence between the full term or shortened term of parliament and the level of intraparlimentary volatility?) or in different parliaments (possible hypotheses to verify: the bigger the parliament, the higher the intraparlimentary volatility; at the bicameral parliaments intraparlimentary volatility is higher than in the unicameral ones; the stronger the democracy, the lower intraparlimentary volatility there are – et cetera). We hope that the results of these analyses can broaden our knowledge about party systems dynamics, as well as influence the quality of parliamentary rules, because the voters receive the tool to assess the stability or fluctuation of MPs that can help to make deputies more accountable for their political decisions.

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